

Cardiological problems of various genesis in patients and the role of the therapist in their timely diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation

Problemas ecardiológicos de diversa génesis en los pacientes y el papel del terapeuta en su diagnóstico oportuno, tratamiento y rehabilitación

149

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Abstract

Cardiological diseases are one of the main causes of mortality and disability of the population, which underlines the importance of their timely detection, prevention and rehabilitation. Various forms of cardiovascular pathologies, including ischaemic heart disease, hypertension, arrhythmias and heart failure, often have latent symptoms or develop against the background of other diseases, which makes early diagnosis difficult. The general practitioner therefore plays a key role in primary care by screening patients and assessing risk factors such as age, family history, lifestyle and comorbidities.

This article reviews the main types of cardiac diseases

and their genesis, as well as algorithms that allow the general practitioner to effectively identify potential problems at an early stage. Symptoms and signs requiring special attention are described, as well as current approaches to monitoring high-risk patients. The need for a multidisciplinary approach, including collaboration between general practitioners and cardiologists, is also discussed to ensure timely referral of patients for advanced testing, specialised treatment and rehabilitation.

Key words: cardiological diseases, therapist, early diagnosis, risk factors, primary care, coronary heart disease, hypertension, arrhythmia, heart failure, screening, interdisciplinary approach, prevention, rehabilitation.

Las enfermedades cardiológicas son una de las principales causas de mortalidad y discapacidad de la población, lo que subraya la importancia de su detección, prevención y rehabilitación oportuna. Diversas formas de patologías cardiovasculares, incluidas la cardiopatía isquémica, la hipertensión, las arritmias y la insuficiencia cardíaca, a menudo tienen síntomas latentes o se desarrollan en el contexto de otras enfermedades, lo que dificulta el diagnóstico precoz. Por tanto, el médico de cabecera desempeña un papel clave en la atención primaria al realizar el cribado de los pacientes y la evaluación de factores de riesgo como la edad, los antecedentes familiares, el estilo de vida y las comorbilidades.

Este artículo revisa los principales tipos de enfermedades cardíacas y su génesis, así como algoritmos que permiten al médico general identificar eficazmente problemas potenciales en una etapa temprana. Se describen los síntomas y signos que requieren atención especial, así como los enfoques actuales para monitorear a los pacientes de alto riesgo. También se analiza la necesidad de un enfoque multidisciplinario, incluida la colaboración entre médicos generales y cardiólogos, para garantizar la derivación oportuna de los pacientes para pruebas avanzadas, tratamiento especializado y rehabilitación.

Palabras clave: enfermedades cardiológicas, terapia, diagnóstico precoz, factores de riesgo, atención primaria, enfermedad coronaria, hipertensión, arritmia, insuficiencia cardíaca, tamizaje, abordaje interdisciplinario, prevención, rehabilitación.

Cardiological diseases are one of the leading causes of mortality and disability in the world, significantly affecting the quality of life and life expectancy of the population. Including a wide range of pathologies such as coronary heart disease, arterial hypertension, arrhythmias and heart failure, these diseases develop against the background of various factors: hereditary predisposition, lifestyle, age-related changes, as well as the presence of comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus and obesity¹. In recent decades, there has been an increasing trend in the incidence of cardiac pathologies in various age groups, which emphasises the need to improve the system of their early detection, prevention and rehabilitation.

Despite advances in diagnosis and treatment, timely detection of cardiovascular disease remains a challenge. Many patients seek help only at the stage of symptom onset, when the disease has already progressed and requires specialised treatment. General practitioners therefore play a key role in the early diagnosis and prevention of cardiac pathologies, as they are the first point of contact and initial screening. Effective screening and assessment of risk factors allow general practitioners to identify hidden forms of disease and make timely lifestyle adjustments, as well as refer patients for in-depth examination and treatment.

This article is devoted to the study of various cardiological diseases, their pathogenesis and specific manifestations, as well as to the analysis of the role of the therapist in their timely detection. Particular attention is paid to algorithms that can be used by general practitioners to assess risk and symptoms signalling possible cardiovascular pathology. The paper considers the possibilities of interdisciplinary approach and the need for interaction between general practitioners and cardiologists for effective patient care and rehabilitation.

Materials and Methods. To write an article on cardiological problems in patients and the role of the therapist in their timely detection, current data on the prevalence and statistics of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) at the level of global and local population were evaluated, age, gender and geographical features of the prevalence of various forms of CVDs were investigated, and the factors influencing the increase in morbidity (urbanisation, population ageing, lifestyle factors) were studied. Such methods as analysis and synthesis of scientific literature, systematic review of publications on cardiological diseases and their classification by type, genesis and risk factors, as well as the study of modern approaches to the diagnosis and early detection of CVDs, with emphasis on the role of the therapist, were applied.

Results

Using the systematisation and classification method, cardiological diseases were classified according to their etiology (e.g. ischaemic heart disease, arterial hypertension, arrhythmias), risk factors (age, hereditary, behavioural) and their impact on the onset and development of CVDs were identified and structured. The systematisation of therapists' approaches to the early diagnosis of CVD, including standard diagnostic algorithms and recommendations, was also carried out.

The method of comparative analysis was also used to compare methods of detection and risk assessment of CVDs in different countries and health care systems. The method of interdisciplinary approach made it possible to study the interaction between general practitioners and other specialists, including cardiologists, endocrinologists, nutritionists, in order to optimise the processes of diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation.

Cardiological diseases, including pathologies such as coronary heart disease, arterial hypertension, arrhythmias and heart failure, are among the most common and dangerous to human life and health². They represent a leading cause of mortality and disability, especially with increasing life expectancy, stress, prevalence of poor nutrition and hypodynamia. Despite advances in medicine and technology, many patients seek help at late stages of the disease, when therapeutic measures are aimed at maintenance rather than complete cure.

These diseases are influenced by a variety of risk factors, including genetic predisposition, age, smoking, unhealthy diet, physical inactivity, chronic stress and the presence of comorbidities such as diabetes and obesity³. It is important to note that many of these factors can be controlled with active patient participation and involvement in the prevention process, which significantly reduces the likelihood of the onset and progression of cardiac disease.

The most important role in the timely detection of cardiological pathologies is played by a general practitioner, a primary care physician, who is the first to contact a patient, assess his or her condition and risk factors. Using screening methods, analysis of complaints and anamnesis, a therapist can suspect cardiovascular pathology at an early stage, which makes it possible to refer the patient for further examination and specialised treatment in time. Thus, a comprehensive approach, including regular check-ups, early diagnosis and prevention, significantly increases the patient's chances of maintaining health and quality of life.

Cardiovascular pathologies such as coronary heart disease, arterial hypertension, arrhythmias and heart failure often develop slowly and may not show clear symptoms in the initial stages. This so-called "hidden symptomatology" complicates their early diagnosis, as patients usually do not present complaints, or write off a slight ailment to fatigue or stress. At the same time, these diseases can progress, gradually damaging the cardiovascular system⁴.

In addition to the absence of symptoms, diagnosis is complicated by the fact that these pathologies often develop against the background of other chronic diseases, such as diabetes mellitus, obesity, chronic kidney disease and metabolic disorders. Associated diseases can mask cardiac pathology or change its clinical picture, which makes it difficult for a therapist or other primary care physician to identify a cardiac problem in a timely manner.

Therefore, screening programmes and systematic monitoring of patients with high risk factors are essential for early diagnosis. Regular preventive check-ups and examinations, such as blood pressure measurements, ECGs, blood tests for lipids and sugar levels, make it possible to detect pathology at an early stage, even in the absence of obvious symptoms. Effective interaction between therapists and cardiologists and other sub-specialists also plays an important role in timely diagnosis and accurate diagnosis.

The therapist, as a primary care physician, plays a crucial role in the health care system because he or she is the first person to encounter a patient and thus has the opportunity to detect cardiological diseases at the earliest stages. One of the main tasks of the therapist is screening - regular examination and monitoring of the patient's health status aimed at identifying risk factors and signs of possible cardiovascular diseases⁵.

Cardiovascular disease screening is a set of diagnostic measures aimed at identifying risk factors and initial signs of disease in patients who may not have any complaints. This process is of key importance in primary health care, as it makes it possible to detect hidden pathologies at a stage when they are still correctable and treatable. Screening is particularly important for people over 40 years of age, patients with a family history, overweight individuals, smokers and those who suffer from chronic stress or have a sedentary lifestyle⁶.

Arterial hypertension is one of the leading risk factors for cardiovascular diseases, including heart attacks and strokes. The therapist regularly measures blood pressure, assessing its stability and compliance with the norm, which helps to detect hypertension in time and start corrective therapy. ECG allows you to detect heart rhythm disorders, ischaemia, signs of myocardial hypertrophy and other abnormalities. It is important to periodically perform ECG even in the absence of complaints,

as many arrhythmias and ischaemic changes can be asymptomatic.

Lipid profile (level of total cholesterol, low and high density lipoproteins, triglycerides) is important to detect dyslipidaemia, one of the key risk factors for atherosclerosis. Analysis of glucose and glycated haemoglobin levels can detect diabetes mellitus or prediabetes, which significantly increase the risk of cardiological diseases.

The marker C-reactive protein (CRP) can indicate the presence of inflammatory processes, which are often associated with cardiovascular disease. Overweight and obesity significantly increase the risk of cardiac disease, so monitoring BMI and body fat helps to identify the need for lifestyle changes and weight loss⁷.

The use of standardised questionnaires (e.g. the SCORE cardiovascular mortality risk scale or Framingham Risk Score) provides an overall picture of a patient's risk. These questionnaires help to take into account many factors, including gender, age, habits, physical activity level, etc.

The therapist collects information about diet, physical activity level, and the presence of unhealthy habits such as smoking and alcohol consumption. This data helps to make recommendations for lifestyle changes that can significantly reduce the risk of cardiac disease. Echocardiography and ultrasound of the carotid arteries and aorta help to assess the structure and function of the heart, the presence of atherosclerotic plaques and the degree of vascular damage⁸.

Screening of cardiovascular diseases allows not only detect the disease at an early stage, but also to take timely measures to reduce the risk of its progression. The earlier signs of pathology are detected, the more opportunities to prevent serious complications such as myocardial infarction and stroke. For the health care system, this means reducing the cost of treating neglected cases and improving the overall statistics on morbidity and mortality from cardiovascular disease.

Ultimately, therapist's screening becomes the foundation of prevention and personalised care for each patient, setting the stage for a healthier and more active population.

Cardiac diseases have many forms, and their causes (genesis) are often related to a combination of genetic, behavioural and metabolic factors. For example, coronary heart disease (CHD) results from inadequate blood supply to the myocardium caused by atherosclerosis of the coronary arteries. Major risk factors include high cholesterol, arterial hypertension, smoking, diabetes and obesity. Atherosclerotic plaques narrow the lumen of blood vessels, which leads to ischaemia and can eventually cause myocardial infarction.

Risk factors should be assessed (history, family predisposition, lifestyle), regular ECGs should be performed,

especially for patients with symptoms such as chest pain, dyspnoea, stress tests and lipid profile analysis to detect cholesterol and lipoprotein levels.

In individual cases, a referral for coronary angiography is necessary to analyse the condition of the coronary vessels in detail.

Arterial hypertension (AH) is characterised by a sustained increase in blood pressure, which over time leads to damage to the blood vessels, heart, kidneys and other organs. The main causes include genetic predisposition, overweight, sedentary lifestyle, stress, excessive salt intake and bad habits⁹.

Patients with blood pressure above 130/80 mmHg are considered a high-risk group. The patient's lifestyle, salt intake, alcohol consumption, stress level are assessed. If necessary, a study of daily monitoring of blood pressure is appointed. Also important are the data of laboratory tests for sodium, potassium, and glucose to exclude concomitant endocrine disorders.

Heart rhythm disorders can be associated with inherited defects, changes in the structure of the heart, e.g. due to heart attack, myocardial hypertrophy, endocrine disorders or electrolyte disturbances. Age and smoking also increase the risk of arrhythmias. To detect arrhythmias, continuous monitoring with ECG, especially for patients with complaints of heart palpitations, rapid or slow heart-beat, if necessary - Holter monitoring (ECG throughout the day). Additional studies of electrolytes, thyroid function analysis are also performed.

Heart failure is often a complication of other diseases such as ischaemic heart disease, arterial hypertension or heart attack. It is characterised by a weakening of the heart's ability to pump a sufficient volume of blood, resulting in insufficient blood supply to tissues¹⁰.

To detect heart failure, anamnesis is collected, symptoms are assessed (dyspnoea, oedema, increased fatigue), physical examination to detect congestion (oedema, dilated neck veins), echocardiography to assess the functional state of the heart and ejection fraction, and analysis of natriuretic peptide (BNP) levels as a marker of heart failure.

Valve abnormalities can be congenital or acquired (due to rheumatism, infective endocarditis, degenerative changes). Valve abnormalities cause backflow of blood, which over time overloads the heart. To detect this pathology, auscultation is performed to detect noises characteristic of valve defects, echocardiography for detailed assessment of the structure and function of the valves, if necessary - referral to MRI or CT scan of the heart to clarify the state of the valve apparatus.

Symptoms and signs that require special attention from the general practitioner when cardiac disease is detected can be varied and depend on the type of disease. However, some common symptoms should alert the GP and prompt further investigation, especially in high-risk patients.

Chest pain is one of the most characteristic symptoms of coronary heart disease. The pain may be tight, squeezing, behind the sternum and radiating to the neck, jaw, shoulder or back. It often occurs with exercise or stress and may be accompanied by shortness of breath, sweating, nausea. This requires immediate examination to exclude myocardial infarction¹¹.

Dyspnoea may be associated with heart failure or other cardiac conditions. It may increase with exercise, lying down or at night, which is an important symptom to diagnose. Swelling is seen in heart failure when the heart cannot pump blood efficiently, causing fluid retention in the body, especially in the legs and abdominal area.

Complaints of a fast or irregular heartbeat, heart palpitations, heart palpitations, weakness or dizziness may be signs of arrhythmias. Longer intervals or a sudden increase in heart rate require diagnosis using ECG and other methods.

Dizziness and fainting can be signs of heart rhythm disturbances, ischaemia or a drop in blood pressure due to insufficient blood supply to the brain. Constant fatigue and decreased physical activity may be manifestations of heart failure, especially if accompanied by shortness of breath and oedema.

Lower extremity pain may indicate peripheral vascular disease (e.g. atherosclerosis), which can lead to poor circulation and an increased risk of stroke or heart attack. Special attention should be paid to patients with hypertension, diabetes, obesity, high cholesterol, and a family history of cardiac disease. In such patients, it is important to regularly monitor the condition and follow the dynamics of their health.

Patients with or at high risk of hypertension should have their blood pressure measured regularly, both in the clinic setting and using diurnal monitoring. The monitoring system allows accurate recording of pressure fluctuations throughout the day and night, which helps to optimise treatment and predict possible complications¹².

Cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), high-density lipoprotein (HDL) and triglyceride levels should be screened regularly. High cholesterol is an important risk factor for atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease.

ECG is one of the main methods for diagnosing arrhythmias, myocardial ischaemia and other heart diseases. For patients with increased risk and symptoms of arrhythmias, regular ECGs are recommended, as well as Holter monitoring (daily ECG recording for 24-48 hours).

Holter monitoring is used to detect hidden heart rhythm abnormalities that may not be apparent on routine examination. Stress tests (e.g. exercise stress tests) can assess heart function under increased physical activity and detect signs of coronary heart disease.

Echocardiography makes it possible to assess the function of the heart, the size of the heart chambers, the presence of heart defects and other diseases. This method is indispensable for the diagnosis of heart failure, valve disease and other structural pathologies of the heart.

For patients at increased risk of cardiac disease, it is important to perform laboratory tests: blood glucose levels to detect diabetes, blood tests for natriuretic peptide levels (markers of heart failure), and tests for C-reactive protein (an indicator of inflammation).

Modern technology allows patients at high risk of cardiovascular disease to monitor their health at home using wearable devices such as smart watches or bracelets to monitor blood pressure, pulse and blood oxygen levels. These devices can send data to a GP for further analysis and treatment adjustments¹³.

Monitoring of the patient's condition requires not only regular check-ups, but also active monitoring of compliance with prescribed therapy. This includes taking anti-hypertensive drugs, statins to lower cholesterol, anticoagulants to prevent thrombosis, and recommendations for lifestyle changes such as weight loss, increased physical activity and smoking cessation.

Various prognostic models such as the Framingham scale or SCORE can be used to assess the risk of cardiovascular disease. These models help to predict the likelihood of developing a heart attack or stroke depending on the patient's risk factors, which helps in deciding on monitoring and treatment strategies.

Thus, the key aspects of monitoring high-risk patients are regular screenings and laboratory tests, the use of modern technologies for health monitoring, and a comprehensive approach including drug treatment and lifestyle correction.

Interdisciplinary approach in healthcare, especially in cardiology, plays a critical role for effective diagnosis, treatment and prevention of cardiovascular disease (CVD). Interaction between general practitioners and cardiologists, as well as with other specialists, is becoming essential for timely detection of diseases at early stages, their in-depth examination and prescription of individualised treatment¹⁴.

Cardiovascular diseases cover a wide range of pathologies such as coronary heart disease, hypertension, arrhythmias, heart failure, heart defects and others. Many of these diseases have a hidden course in the early stages, which requires special attention to the risks and the need for more in-depth screening. General practitioners play a key role in primary diagnosis, but cardiologists, who have a more specialised and in-depth knowledge of cardiology, need to be involved to make an accurate diagnosis and prescribe specific therapy¹⁵.

Early detection of cardiovascular disease through effective screening and diagnosis allows cardiologists to prescribe the necessary specialised treatment at an earlier stage of the disease, which can significantly improve the patient's prognosis and quality of life, and reduce the risk of serious complications such as myocardial infarction, stroke or chronic heart failure¹⁶.

The therapist, as the primary care physician, performs the initial examination of the patient and identifies symptoms or risk factors that may indicate possible cardiovascular disease. At this stage, the therapist may perform initial examinations such as blood pressure measurement, ECG, and assess the presence of risk factors¹⁷. When signs of disease become evident or the patient's health risk is high, the therapist should refer the patient to a cardiologist for a more in-depth examination (e.g. echocardiography, coronarography, stress tests and other specialised diagnostic techniques).

In the case of rare, complex or multicomponent cardiac diseases (e.g. genetic heart diseases, rare forms of arrhythmias, and combinations of cardiovascular disease with endocrine disorders or renal disease), the general practitioner and cardiologist may work in close collaboration. For example, the general practitioner may notice common symptoms that require further evaluation, while the cardiologist develops an individualised treatment plan and manages the patient in a patient-specific manner.

Collaboration between the internist and cardiologist results in a more effective patient education program. The therapist plays an important role in teaching the patient the basics of cardiovascular disease prevention (eg, healthy eating, smoking cessation, stress reduction, physical activity), and the cardiologist - in explaining the features of treatment and management of the disease, including prescribing medications and monitoring their effectiveness¹⁸.

Modern treatment of cardiological diseases requires a comprehensive approach, including drug therapy (anti-hypertensive drugs, statins, anticoagulants, heart failure drugs, etc.) and lifestyle adjustments. Cardiologists can prescribe specific therapy, and therapists should monitor the general condition of the patient, control comorbidities, such as diabetes and obesity, which may affect the cardiovascular system¹⁹.

One of the key aspects of a multidisciplinary approach is disease prevention. The therapist and cardiologist can

work together to develop individualised prevention programmes for high-risk patients. This may include advice on diet, physical activity, weight management and stress levels. It is also important that the cardiologist monitors the patient's condition as part of secondary prevention - reducing the risk of recurrent cardiac events in people who have had a myocardial infarction or stroke.

Interaction between a therapist and a cardiologist allows for more accurate and timely detection of cardiological diseases. The cardiologist, as a specialist, can offer additional diagnostic methods that are not available at the level of primary medicine, which contributes to a more accurate diagnosis.

Prompt referral of a patient to a cardiologist in case of suspected serious cardiac disease facilitates early initiation of treatment, which can significantly improve prognosis and prevent the development of complications.

Patients who receive integrated care, including multi-specialist input, feel more confident in their treatment. Working together with a general practitioner and a cardiologist provides patients with a more personalised and attentive approach.

Timely and effective communication between therapist and cardiologist helps to avoid prolonged and costly procedures and reduces complications and hospitalisations, which ultimately reduces the financial burden on the healthcare system²⁰.

An interdisciplinary approach in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases, based on the interaction between therapists and cardiologists, is crucial for timely diagnosis, effective treatment and prevention of diseases. This allows not only to improve the quality of life of patients, but also to increase the efficiency of the healthcare system as a whole. The coordinated work of specialists at different levels allows for an individualized approach to each patient and increases the chances of successful treatment and reduction of mortality from cardiovascular diseases.

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) remain one of the leading causes of mortality and disability of the population, which underlines the importance of their timely detection. Early detection of cardiological pathologies can significantly reduce the risk of severe complications such as myocardial infarction, stroke and heart failure and improve patient prognosis. Therefore, the key role in early diagnosis and prevention of these diseases belongs to the therapist, who is the first to assess the patient's condition, conduct screening and identify risk factors.

Modern medicine requires a comprehensive approach to the diagnosis and treatment of cardiological diseases. A therapist, performing initial examination and screening, can detect the first signs of disease, but more accurate diagnosis and prescription of specific therapy require the involvement of cardiologists and other specialised specialists. This interaction ensures accurate diagnosis, reduces the risk of errors and ensures timely prescription of effective treatment.

An interdisciplinary approach based on co-operation between general practitioners and cardiologists is the key to successful treatment of cardiovascular diseases. Collaboration between these specialists enables not only deeper diagnosis and treatment, but also effective management of patients with combined diseases, such as arterial hypertension, diabetes, and obesity, which increase the risk of CVDs. Regular consultations and joint decision-making on treatment issues contribute to optimising therapy and improving treatment outcomes.

For effective prevention and control of cardiovascular diseases, it is important to regularly monitor high-risk patients, which includes blood pressure measurement, lipid profile analysis, electrocardiography and echocardiography. Modern technologies and wearable devices can further facilitate monitoring of the patient's condition at home, providing physicians with relevant information for timely decision-making.

The therapist plays a key role not only in detecting cardiological diseases, but also in preventing their development. Regular counselling on healthy lifestyle, proper nutrition, physical activity and avoidance of bad habits (smoking, alcohol) can significantly reduce the risk of CVDs. It is important that GPs actively participate in the secondary prevention programme - reducing the likelihood of disease recurrence in patients who already have cardiovascular problems.

Early referral of patients with suspected cardiac disease to a specialist can significantly increase the chances of successful treatment. Cardiologists are more specialised

and can offer more precise diagnostic methods such as stress tests, coronarography, echocardiography and other procedures that allow a more accurate assessment of the condition of the heart and blood vessels.

The coordinated work of a therapist and a cardiologist allows not only to treat the disease effectively, but also to actively educate the patient on the importance of adhering to prescriptions, monitoring health and maintaining a healthy lifestyle. Constant contact with the patient at all stages of treatment contributes to better compliance with recommendations and, as a result, better clinical results.

Cardiological diseases require timely diagnosis, a comprehensive approach and effective treatment. The therapist, as a primary care physician, plays a key role in early detection of diseases and referral of patients to cardiologists for in-depth examination and specialised therapy. Interaction between therapists and cardiologists, as well as the use of modern methods of monitoring and prevention, contribute not only to improving patient health, but also to reducing the burden on the health care system. Thus, timely referral to specialized care and interdisciplinary work are important factors contributing to successful treatment of cardiovascular disease and rehabilitation.

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